

DRUG UTILIZATION PATTERN IN OTORHINOLARYNGOLOGY OUTPATIENT DEPARTMENT: A CROSS-SECTIONAL STUDY IN A TERTIARY CARE TEACHING HOSPITAL, MIMS, MANDYA***Dr. Arpitha T. K.,¹Ms. Nisarga H. R.,³Mr. Muhthasim Akber K.**

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ABSTRACT

Background: Ear, Nose and Throat (ENT) disorders constitute a significant portion of morbidity in both urban and rural populations, contributing substantially to (OPD) visits across all age groups. Conditions such as otitis media, hearing loss, allergic rhinitis, pharyngitis, ringing sensation in the ear, sinusitis, tonsillitis and vertigo are frequently encountered in ENT OPDs. These disorders, while often non-life threatening, can significantly impact quality of life, and in some cases, may lead to serious complications if not managed properly. The prescribing pattern reflects the prescriber's clinical judgement, adherence to treatment guidelines. Monitoring and evaluating prescribing trends in ENT OPDs are essential to promote the rational use of medicines, ensure adherence to essential drug lists, and align practice with WHO core prescribing indicators. **Objective:** To analyse and to evaluate prescribing pattern using WHO core prescribing indicators. **Methods And Methodology:** A cross-sectional study was conducted. Patients who visited the ENT OPD and met the inclusion criteria had their pertinent data obtained from their prescriptions. **Results:** This study analysed 200 prescriptions from the ENT outpatient department of MIMS Teaching Hospital, Mandya. Males (56%) were more affected than females (44%), with middle-aged patients (41-60 years, 32%) representing the largest group. Earache (20%) and throat pain (14.5%) were the most common presenting symptoms. The average number of drugs per prescription was 3.17, indicating polypharmacy, with most containing two to four drugs. Among 634 drugs prescribed, antihistamines (25.53%) were most frequent, followed by antibiotics (19.72%) and analgesics (14.67%), with CTZ and Cefixime being the leading agents. Tablets were the predominant dosage form (72.88%), and most drugs were prescribed by generic name (96.05%). Supportive non-pharmacological measures, such as keeping the ear dry (42.46%) and steam inhalation (24.66%), were also recommended. WHO prescribing indicators showed higher than standard drug use per encounter but near-ideal generic and essential medicine prescribing, while injection use was absent due to the outpatient setting. Overall, prescribing practices were largely rational, though polypharmacy was notable. **Conclusion:** The study evaluated prescribing patterns in the ENT outpatient department. Most drugs were prescribed as oral solids, mainly from the WHO Essential Drug List, with generics preferred to reduce patient costs. Ear-related complaints were most common, followed by throat and nasal conditions. Findings emphasize rational drug use, patient education, and the need for periodic drug utilization studies to optimize therapy.

KEYWORDS: Ear, Nose and Throat, Outpatient department, World Health organization, Drug utilization studies.

1. INTRODUCTION

Otorhinolaryngology, can also be called as otolaryngology, is a medical and surgical specialty

concerned with the diagnosis, management, and treatment of diseases and disorders of the ear, nose, and throat (ENT) and related structures of the head and neck,

including the sinuses, larynx (voice box), oral cavity, and upper pharynx (mouth and throat).^[1] An otolaryngologist treats issues in your ears, nose, and throat, as well as related areas in your head and neck. They are called as ENT doctors or ENTs for short.^[2]

1.1 EAR ANATOMY

Ears are not just for hearing – they are also important for

controlling position sense and balance. Each ear is divided into 3 sections: The outer; the middle; and inner ear. The middle and inner parts of the year are located in hollow cavities on either side of the head within the temporal bones of the skull. The tympanic membrane (eardrum) separates the outer and middle ear. The main function of the ear is hearing and balancing.^[3]

Figure-01: Ear Anatomy.

OUTER EAR

Also called as external ear is the part of ear that's visible. Even called as auricle or pinna, the outer ear consists of ridged cartilage and skin, and it contains glands that secrete earwax. It's funnel-shaped canal leads to eardrum, or tympanic membrane.

MIDDLE EAR

The middle ear begins on the other side of tympanic membrane (eardrum). There are three tiny bones in this area- the malleus, incus and stapes. They transfer sound vibrations from eardrum to inner ear. The middle ear also houses the eustachian tubes, which help equalize the air pressure in the ears.

INNER EAR

The inner ear contains two main parts: the cochlea and the semicircular canals. The cochlea is the hearing organ. This snail – shaped structure contains two fluid-filled chambers lined with tiny hairs. When sound enters, the fluid inside of your cochlea causes the tiny hairs to vibrate, sending electrical impulses to your brain.

EAR FUNCTIONS

1. Sound Collection (Outer Ear)
2. Direction Detection
3. Protection of Inner Structures

4. Vibration Transmission (Middle Ear)
5. Pressure Equalization (Eustachian Tube)
6. Amplification of Sound
7. Signal Conversion (Inner Ear - Cochlea)
8. Frequency Differentiation (Basilar Membrane)
9. Auditory Signal Transmission to Brain (Auditory Nerve)
10. Balance Maintenance (Vestibular System)

1.2 NOSE ANATOMY

Nose, a structure that sticks out from the middle of the face, is the entrance to respiratory system. It warms, conditions and filters the air you breathe. It also houses the olfactory organs, which give you the sense of smell. Nose are somewhat pyramid-shaped, and they come in all sizes. The nasal bone and cartilage play a major role in the nose shape.^[3]

Figure- 02: Nose anatomy.

PARTS OF NOSE

The outside parts of the nose (the parts you can see) consists of bone, cartilage and fatty tissue. It includes.

NASAL ROOT: The top root of the nose located between your eyebrows, where your nose connects to your face.

NASAL APEX: The bottom part of your nose that houses your nostrils and tapers off into a rounded tip.

NASAL DORSUM: The middle part of your nose, between your nasal root and nasal apex.

CILIA: These tiny, hairlike structures trap dirt and particles.

NASAL CAVITIES: These are hollow spaces where air flows in and out. You have two of them- one on each side. Mucus membranes line your nasal cavities.

NERVE CELLS: These cells communicate with your brain and give you your sense of smell.

NOSE HAIRS: The hairs inside your nose trap dirt and dust that would otherwise end up in your nasal passages.

NOSTRILS (nares): The nostrils are holes that lead to the nasal passages.

PARANASAL SINUSES: These air- filled pockets connect to your nasal cavities. They produce the mucus that keeps your nose moist.

SEPTUM: This is the bone and cartilage that separate your nasal cavities. The lower part of your septum sits between your nostrils.

TURBINATES (conchae): These folds warm and moisten air after you breathe in it. They also aid in nasal drainage. You have three pairs of turbinates along each of your nasal cavities.

FUNCTIONS OF NOSE

- ◆ Air Filtration – Traps dust, microbes, and other particles using nasal hairs and mucus.
- ◆ Warming of Air – Warms the incoming air before it reaches the lungs.
- ◆ Humidification – Adds moisture to inhaled air to protect the respiratory tract.
- ◆ Smell Detection (Olfaction) – Senses and identifies odours through olfactory receptors.
- ◆ Speech Resonance – Enhances the quality and tone of voice during speech.
- ◆ Protection Response – Detects irritants and triggers sneezing to expel them.

1.3 THROAT (pharynx) ANATOMY

Throat also called as pharynx is a multitasking muscular funnel that helps you breathe and directs food and liquid to your digestive system. It includes nasopharynx, oropharynx, and laryngopharynx. Pharynx located in the middle of the neck. It sits below the lower part of the skull and just above your esophagus and larynx.^[3]

PARTS OF PHARYNX (Throat)

NASOPHARYNX: At the top of your throat. It connects your nose to your respiratory system.

OROPHARYNX: In the middle of your throat. It contains your tonsils at the base of your tongue and connects to your oral cavity. Air, food and fluid all pass

through your pharynx.

LARYNGOPHARYNX: At the bottom of your pharynx. It regulates how food moves to your esophagus and on to your digestive system, and how air moves to your lungs.

Anatomy of the Pharynx

Figure- 03: Pharynx anatomy.

FUNCTION: In general, it supports the respiratory and digestive system:

- ◆ Routes air coming in your nose and mouth down to your larynx (voice box), which in turn, moves air to your trachea and lungs.
- ◆ Delivers food and liquid to your esophagus, which sends them on to your stomach.
- ◆ Pharynx helps to make sure particles of food and liquid don't tumble into your trachea and your lungs.

1.4 PREVALENECE OF ENT DISEASE CONDITIONS

Ear, Nose, Throat (ENT) infections are common clinical problems, which affect majority of the population, and are a cause of serious morbidity and debility.^[4] Diseases related to Ear, Nose and Throat (ENT) occur very commonly in both pediatric as well as adult age groups often leading to significant impairment of accustomed daily pursuits in adult age groups which might lead to work loss and wage loss in them as well as absenteeism from schools in children. This often hampers their academics and normal routine activities.^[5]

In 2011, the prevalence of disabling hearing loss was approximately 360 million people it estimated that around 15% of the world's adult population live with a

hearing loss. It is also responsible for 94.6 disability adjusted life years (DALY's) lost worldwide, contributing to 6.2% of all disability adjusted life years.^[6]

An upper respiratory infection (URI) is a viral or bacterial infection that affects the nose, throat (pharynx), sinuses and voice box (larynx) the most familiar upper respiratory infections include the common cold (rhinopharyngitis), infection of the throat (pharyngitis), tonsils (tonsilitis), the maxillary sinuses behind the nose (sinusitis), and the larynx (laryngitis). Ear infections (acute otitis media) are another manifestation of URI. According to a recent study, acute respiratory infections are the most frequent reason for seeking medical attention and are the reason for 75% of the antibiotic prescriptions each year. As these ENT infections are generally caused by microorganisms such as bacteria, fungi and viruses, the ultimate aim of the drug therapy of ENT infections is to eradicate infections and minimize the morbidity and complications associated with them by using appropriate antimicrobials. An ear infection is caused by a bacteria or virus in the middle ear. Mainly ear pain, fullness in ear, hearing loss, ringing in the ears, discharge, nausea, vomiting and vertigo are the symptoms of ear infection. Some other ear diseases are

otitis media with effusion and fluid buildup in the middle ear and chronic suppurative otitis media, a persistent ear infection resulting in tearing or perforation of the eardrum. Sinus infection is the mostly common disease of nose. Teeny holes that connect nasal passage to sinuses get blocked and causing growth of microorganisms leads to sinus infection.^[7]

Diseases related to ear, nose and throat (ENT) has serious public health problems both in rural and urban population. Knowledge of prevalence of ENT disease in a particular region is important to estimate the magnitude and distribution of morbidity in order to formulate appropriate measures to manage such cases.^[8]

Many developing countries have few experts and very poor facilities to support the experts and thus creates a very heavy workload on otorhinolaryngologists. There are a lot of ENT diseases which range from minor problems like allergies to severe problems like malignancies which affect lives of people and is becoming a public health problem. Some ENT diseases are congenital and others are acquired. The acquired causes may be trauma, infections, inflammation, vascular and neurological. Some are of acute while others are of chronic onset.^[9]

The types of ENT diseases vary from country to country. For Nigeria, the prevalence of diseases of ear, nose and throat were 62.7%, 23.0% and 9.6%, respectively. In Senegal, the rates were 22.8%, 54.6% and 22.4% and in India, the rates were 36.6%, 23.5%, and 16.58% respectively.^[10]

Otitis Media is highly prevalent worldwide and is the main cause of hearing impairment in developing countries.^[11] World Health Organization (WHO) has reported that hearing impairment in 42 million people (above 3 years) in the world was mainly caused by OM

(Otitis Media). The prevalence of OM varies in different countries, populations and ethnic groups. Studies around the world have reported that the prevalence of Acute Suppurative Otitis Media (ASOM) varies from 2.3% to 20%, CSOM 4% to 33.3%, and OME from 1.3% to 31.3%. The prevalence rate of ASOM in India is around 17-20%, CSOM is 7.8% and OME is not yet known.^[12]

Otitis Externa is common all over the world, with a higher incidence in tropical than in temperate zones because of the higher temperature and humidity. Its lifetime prevalence is estimated at 10%. It affects adults most commonly, and children only rarely.^[13] The prevalence of chronic rhinosinusitis (CRS) measured in epidemiologic studies is 5% to 12%. About 44-87% of patients with rhinitis may have a combination of allergic and non-allergic rhinitis.^[14] Sore throat and pharyngitis represent more than 2% and 5% of all outpatient primary care visits for adult and pediatric populations, respectively.^[15] Acute laryngitis can affect patients of any age, though is more common in the adult population, usually affecting individuals aged 18 to 40, though it may be seen in children as young as three.^[16]

1.5 RISK FACTORS OF ENT DISEASE CONDITIONS

Understanding the risk factors for ear, nose and throat (ENT) diseases is crucial for early detection, prevention, and management. Below is a structured overview of the key risk factors associated with major ENT disease categories.

1.5.1 COMMON RISK FACTORS ACROSS EAR DISORDERS

To facilitate a clearer understanding of the predisposing factors, the commonly reported risk factors for ear disorders are systematically presented in the following table.

Table- 1: common risk factors across ear disorders.

	Risk Factor	Description
	Age	Young children (under 3 years) are prone due to immature anatomy and immunity; elderly face age-related hearing decline.
	Exposure to Cigarette Smoke	Passive and active smoke cause inflammation and increase ear infection risk.
	Allergies & Respiratory Illnesses	Allergies and frequent colds cause Eustachian tube blockage and middle ear infections.
	Group Childcare	Exposure to densely populated daycare environments increases likelihood of infections in children.
	Bottle Feeding	Infants who are bottle-fed have a greater risk of ear infections than breastfed infants.
	Loud Noise Exposure	Repeated loud noise intake damages inner ear structures, causing hearing loss over time.

1.5.2 COMMON RISK FACTORS ACROSS NOSE DISORDERS

Nasal disorders are influenced by a variety of intrinsic

and extrinsic factors; the table below highlights the most commonly identified risk contributors.

Table- 2: Common risk factors across nose disorders.

	Risk Factor	Description
	Allergies	Hypersensitivity to allergens like pollen, dust mites, or pet dander can cause chronic nasal inflammation, leading to rhinitis and sinusitis.
	Environmental Pollutants	Exposure to air pollution, smoke (including secondhand smoke), and other airborne irritants can damage nasal passages and increase inflammation.
	Occupational Exposure	Certain professions involve exposure to dust, chemicals, or fumes that can irritate the nasal lining and lead to chronic nasal conditions.
	Asthma	Individuals with asthma often experience nasal inflammation and are at a higher risk of developing chronic sinusitis and nasal polyps due to shared inflammatory pathways.
	Structural Abnormalities	Physical issues such as a deviated septum or enlarged turbinates can impede airflow and mucus drainage, leading to recurrent infections and chronic congestion.
	Weakened Immune System	Conditions that compromise the body's immune defenses make individuals more susceptible to nasal infections, including bacterial or fungal sinusitis.

1.5.3 COMMON RISK FACTORS ACROSS THROAT DISORDERS

The table below categorizes the principal risk factors

contributing to throat disorders, serving as a reference for further clinical evaluation and research.

Table 3: Common risk factors across throat disorders.

	Risk Factor	Description
	Smoking & Tobacco Use	Irritates throat lining, weakens immunity, increases infection and cancer risk.
	Alcohol Consumption	Causes chronic irritation and elevates risk of throat cancer.
	Acid Reflux (GERD)	Stomach acid irritating the throat mucosa leads to inflammation and soreness.
	Exposure to Infections	Contact with infected persons raises chances of viral and bacterial throat infections.
	Weakened Immune System	Conditions like HIV, stress, or medication reduce resistance to infections.
	Age	Young children and older adults are more vulnerable to infections and malignancies.
	Poor Oral Hygiene	Increases bacterial colonization, facilitating throat infections.

1.6 RATIONAL DRUG USE (RDU)

Rational drug use (RDU) generally covers appropriate prescribing, appropriate dispensing and appropriate patient use of medicines for the diagnosis, prevention, mitigation and treatment of diseases. RDU can also be described as safe, cost-effective and economically viable use of drugs.

To enhance RDU, the patient should receive medicines appropriate to their health care conditions, at optimum

doses and sufficient time, as well as at the cost that the individual and the community can afford.^[17] Irrational prescribing and inappropriate use of medicines results in wastage of available therapeutic resources, higher cost of treatment and adverse clinical conditions like ineffective and unsafe treatment, exacerbation or prolongation of existing illness, iatrogenic illness, increasing resistance to antimicrobials an ultimately an undue distress and harm to the patient.

Figure- 04: Rational use of drugs.

1.7 WHO/INRUD CORE PRESCRIBING INDICATORS

WHO in collaboration with the International Network for the Rational Use of Drug (INRUD) developed core indicators for assessing drug use. These indicators are widely accepted as a global standard for identification of some common problems associated with prescribing such as polypharmacy, inclination of prescribers for branded products, deviation from essential medicines list. The WHO/INRUD core indicators that are using to describe

the drug use are as follows.

- ◆ Average number of drugs per encounter.
- ◆ Percentage of drugs prescribed by generic name.
- ◆ Percentage of encounters with an antibiotic described.
- ◆ Percentage of drugs prescribed from WHO essential drug list.
- ◆ Percentage of fixed drug combination from WHO essential drug list.^[18]

Table 4: WHO Core prescribing indicators.

INDICATORS	STANDARD VALUES
Average number of drugs per encounter	1.6-1.8
Percentage of encounters with an antibiotic prescribed	20.0-26.8
Percentage of encounters with an injection prescribed	13.4-24.1
Percentage of drugs prescribed by generic name	100.0
Percentage of drugs prescribed from essential drug list/formulary	100.0

This study utilized above core indicators to describe the drug use patterns in ENT department of tertiary care teaching hospital.

2. AIM AND OBJECTIVES

2.1 AIM

ENT diseases significantly affect the quality of life in both adults and children. Infections, particularly upper respiratory tract infections (URTIs), remain the major

cause worldwide, often leading to complications such as hearing loss and learning disabilities in children.

Drug Use Evaluation (DUE) is a continuous, structured quality improvement process that reviews prescribing practices, provides feedback to clinicians, establishes standards for rational drug use, and promotes patient education and counselling.

2.2 OBJECTIVE

PRIMARY OBJECTIVE

- ❖ To analyse the prescription pattern of the drugs used in the patients attending OPD of the ENT department, of Mandy institute of Medical Science.

SECONDARY OBJECTIVE

- ❖ To assess the rationality of these prescriptions using WHO core drug prescribing indicators.

3. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

3.1 ACCORDING TO EARLIER STUDIES CONDUCTED

◆ **Abubakar K *et al.*, (2014)** performed a six-month prospective study at the National Ear Care Centre's outpatient department in Kaduna, Nigeria, focusing on drug prescription patterns for chronic suppurative otitis media (CSOM). Utilizing WHO/INRUD core prescribing indicators, they discovered that children represented 60.6% of CSOM cases, with otorrhea as the predominant symptom (85.2%). Antibiotics were the most frequently prescribed drugs (48%) quinolones, followed by antihistamines (21.5%). Injections were administered in 22.54% of cases, and only 23.22% of prescriptions utilized generic names. Each prescription averaged 7.1 medications, with oral forms being the most prevalent (78.4%).^[4]

◆ **Nidhi Kumari *et al.*, (2022)** conducted a study to assess drug prescription patterns in the ENT OPD and analyze ADRs from the ENT Department (IPD & OPD). This six-month observational and prospective study, carried out from March to October 2021, evaluated 251 patient prescriptions for demographics, medication patterns, types of ENT diseases, and prescription completeness. ADRs were monitored through active surveillance and spontaneous reporting. The findings indicated a male predominance (64.5%) among patients, with a total of 850 medications prescribed, predominantly antimicrobials. The most frequently used fixed-dose combination was cefpodoxime with clavulanic acid, and otitis media was the most common ENT condition. All prescriptions included dosage, frequency, treatment duration, and instructions in the local language. 3.3 drugs were prescribed per patient, with none exceeding five medications, reflecting a cautious approach to polypharmacy.^[5]

◆ **Sudhir L Padwal and *et al.*, (2015)** conducted a cross-sectional observational study over three months at the ENT outpatient department of SRTR Government Medical College, Ambajogai, Maharashtra. Using WHO prescribing indicators, the study assessed 855 patient cases involving 3342 drug prescriptions—averaging 3.9 drugs prescribed and 2.5 dispensed per case. Male patients represented 59.64% of the sample. Antibiotics were prescribed in 97.19% of cases, making them the most common drug class (24.86%), followed by NSAIDs (23.60%), gastroprotective (22.55%), and antihistamines (19.92%). Oral route was preferred (97.75%), and 80% of prescriptions used brand names. The findings raise concerns about polypharmacy, excessive antibiotic use,

and reliance on branded drugs, indicating a symptomatic treatment approach.^[6]

◆ **Mst. Marium Begum *et al.*, (2016)** performed a cross-sectional, observational, and prospective study in the ENT departments of various public and private hospitals in Dhaka, including Dhaka Medical College and Hospital and Mitford Hospital. The study involved 300 patients, with 73.33% being male and 87.33% being outpatients. Analysis revealed that 93.33% of prescriptions included antibiotics, with all containing antibiotics along with other medications—proton pump inhibitors (80.67%), analgesics (76.67%), and vitamin/iron supplements (51.33%). Approximately 81% of prescriptions had two antibiotics, while about 19% had one; none exceeded two. Oral administration was predominant, mainly through tablets (80%) and capsules (12%). Among 473 prescribed antibiotics, 54% were from the β -lactam class, and 46.33% were cephalosporins. Most antibiotics (92%) were prescribed by brand names.^[7]

◆ **Amardeep Singh *et al.*, (2019)** conducted a retrospective study based on outpatient medical records from the Department of Otorhinolaryngology at Basaveshwara Medical College and Hospital, Chitradurga, Karnataka. The analysis revealed that ear-related conditions constituted the largest group of ENT cases (40.4%), followed by throat disorders (28.5%). Within the ear category, otitis media was most prevalent (19.7%), while pharyngitis (12.8%) and tonsillitis (8.0%) were common throat issues. Nasal problems were mainly attributed to allergic rhinitis (7.0%) and deviated nasal septum (6.5%). The findings indicate that infections in the ear and throat form the bulk of ENT problems, most of which are preventable. Enhancing public health education can play a crucial role in reducing the incidence and associated complications of these conditions.^[8]

◆ **Muhammad Zeeshan *et al.*, (2018)** conducted a study at Ayub Teaching Hospital using non-probability sampling to examine 250 ENT patients at the outpatient department. The sample included 51.6% males and 48.4% females, with most belonging to a low socio-economic background and having primary or matric-level education. Ear conditions were most prevalent, particularly bilateral ear wax (15.2%), acute otitis media (13.2%), and chronic suppurative otitis media (10.8%). Throat issues followed, with tonsillitis being the most common (15.6%). Nasal problems were mainly allergic rhinitis (13.2%) and deviated nasal septum (8%).^[9]

◆ **Ayotunde James Fasunla *et al.*, (2013)** conducted a study at the University College Hospital's Department of Otorhinolaryngology. Out of 5,001 patients, 52.8% were male (2,641) and 47.2% were female (2,360). Approximately 41% (2,050 patients) were aged 15 or younger. In terms of religion, 63% identified as Christian, 37% as Muslim, and less than 1% followed other faiths. A greater number of patients came from lower occupational classes compared to higher ones. On average, 83 cases of ear, nose, and throat (ENT) conditions were treated monthly. Ear diseases were the

most common (62.7%; 3,136 patients), followed by nose issues (23.0%; 1,153), throat disorders (9.6%; 479), and head/neck diseases (4.7%; 233). In children (≤ 15 years), prevalent ENT conditions included otitis media, obstructive adenoid, foreign bodies in the ear, and throat infections. Conversely, patients aged 16 and older most often presented with hearing loss, rhinosinusitis, and tumors.^[10]

◆ **Lorenzo Monasta *et al.*, (2012)** A global study investigated the incidence, risk factors, and outcomes of otitis media (OM) using a two-phase method involving risk factor analysis and regression modeling. It estimated that acute OM (AOM) affects about 709 million people each year, with 51% of cases in children under five. Chronic suppurative OM (CSOM) has an incidence of 4.76 per 1,000, totaling around 31 million cases annually—22.6% in young children. OM-related hearing loss affects 30.82 per 10,000 people, and roughly 21,000 deaths per year are attributed to OM complications.^[11]

◆ **Manche Santoshi Kumari *et al.*, (2016)** A study conducted at MAA ENT Hospitals in Hyderabad (2004–2014) analyzed 2,602 patients with otitis media (OM), including both adults and children. Diagnoses were confirmed by ENT specialists. The most common type was squamous-chronic suppurative OM (47.3%), strongly linked to tinnitus. Mucosal-chronic OM (18.5%) was often bilateral and associated with tinnitus and vertigo. Acute OM affected 17.6%, while OM with effusion (16.6%) was linked to adenoids, snoring, and hearing issues. The study highlighted OM's broad impact and its association with hearing loss.^[12]

◆ **Susanne Wiegand *et al.*, (2019)** A literature review on otitis externa highlighted that acute cases are best managed with pain relief, ear canal cleaning, and topical antibiotics or corticosteroids, which improve symptoms like inflammation and discharge. Though large trials are limited, antimicrobials outperform placebos. Oral antibiotics are recommended for systemic spread or in immunocompromised or diabetic patients. Chronic otitis externa is often linked to skin disorders, while malignant otitis externa—a severe infection involving nearby bone—mainly affects older adults with diabetes or weakened immunity. Early, accurate diagnosis ensures targeted treatment and helps prevent complications or progression.^[13]

◆ **Dirk Dietz De Loos *et al.*, (2018)** A study involving 834 participants evaluated the prevalence of chronic rhinosinusitis (CRS) by combining symptom-based EPOS criteria with imaging evidence (Lund-Mackay scores). Of the total, 107 individuals (12.8%) met EPOS diagnostic criteria. However, among them, 50% had no radiologic findings (LM score = 0), 26% had mild findings (LM 1–3), and 23% had significant opacification (LM ≥ 4). Based on imaging alone, 3.0% of the total population met criteria for clinically confirmed CRS (LM ≥ 4), while 6.4% had any radiologic evidence (LM > 0). Among participants without upper airway symptoms, 12% still had LM scores ≥ 4 . Additionally, allergic rhinitis was present in 20% of participants.^[14]

◆ **Behnam Sadeghird *et al.*, (2017)** A review of 10 clinical trials with 1,426 participants found that a single low dose of oral corticosteroids (mainly dexamethasone ≤ 10 mg) significantly improved sore throat pain relief. Patients were over twice as likely to feel relief within 24 hours (RR 2.2) and 1.5 times more likely to be pain-free at 48 hours (RR 1.5). Pain relief began 4.8 hours earlier, and complete relief occurred 11.1 hours sooner. Pain scores were 1.3 points lower at 24 hours. Most studies reported no or only mild, comparable side effects. Overall, low-dose corticosteroids were effective and safe for short-term use, but long-term risks remain unclear.^[15]

◆ **Mekonnen Sisay *et al.*, (2017)** A cross-sectional study was conducted at three hospitals in eastern Ethiopia—Dilchora Referral Hospital, Hiwot Fana Specialized University Hospital, and Karamara General Hospital—to evaluate rational drug use using WHO core indicators. On average, 2.34 drugs were prescribed per encounter. Antibiotics were included in 57.87% of prescriptions, and injectables in 10.9%. The average consultation time was 276.5 seconds, while dispensing time averaged 61.12 seconds. About 75.77% of prescribed medicines were actually dispensed, but only 3.3% of prescriptions were properly labeled. Around 75.7% of patients correctly understood their dosage instructions. Of the 30 key drugs, 20 (66.7%) were in stock, with 19 (63.3%) labeled correctly. Stockouts lasted about 30 days annually.^[17]

◆ **Muhammad Atif *et al.*, (2016)**. This study looked at how medicines are used in the outpatient departments of two hospitals in Bahawalpur, Pakistan, using WHO/INRUD guidelines. It found that, on average, 2.8 drugs were given per prescription. Only 56.6% were prescribed by generic name, and over half (51.5%) included antibiotics. No injections were used, and most drugs (98.8%) were from the Essential Drugs List. The average consultation time was just 1.2 minutes, and dispensing time was only 8.7 seconds. While nearly all drugs were dispensed and properly labelled, only 61.6% of patients understood how to take them correctly. All departments had the EDL, but only 72.4% of essential medicines were in stock. The study found signs of irrational drug use, such as overprescribing, brand-name use, high antibiotic use, short consultation times, and poor patient understanding. Improvements are needed to promote safer and more effective medicine use.^[18]

◆ **Paul Schaefer *et al.*, (2012)** proposed an Acute otitis externa: an update, which explains Acute otitis externa is inflammation of the ear canal, usually caused by *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* or *Staphylococcus aureus*, often after swimming or ear trauma. Symptoms include ear pain, itching, discharge, and tenderness when moving the tragus or pinna. Treatment involves topical antibiotics (e.g., acetic acid, aminoglycosides, polymyxin B, quinolones), sometimes combined with corticosteroids for faster relief. Choice depends on tympanic membrane status, side effects, cost, and patient compliance. Oral antibiotics are used for severe or spreading infections. Chronic cases are linked to allergies or skin conditions

and require addressing the underlying cause.^[20]

◆ **Ann M Aring *et al.*, (2011)** proposed a review article on Acute rhinosinusitis in adults and explains about Rhinosinusitis is a common condition with types including acute (viral or bacterial), subacute, recurrent acute, and chronic. Most acute cases are viral and linked to the common cold. Mild symptoms are treated with analgesics, decongestants, and saline nasal spray. Antibiotics (e.g., amoxicillin) are used if symptoms persist beyond 7 days or worsen. Intranasal steroids may help, but evidence is limited. Imaging is not needed for uncomplicated cases; CT is reserved for complications or persistent symptoms. Rare complications include orbital, brain, or bone involvement. ENT referral is advised if symptoms continue despite full treatment.^[21]

◆ **O Dobrescu *et al.*, (1992)** proposed a review article on Acute laryngitis in children which explains the following Acute laryngitis is the most common form of upper airway obstruction in young children. Laryngeal obstruction requiring hospitalization and sometimes intubation may be due to viral infection or occasionally to allergic reaction. The natural course of the disease is impossible to predict; therefore, repeated clinical assessments are needed. Continuous worsening of dyspnea may suggest a diagnosis of bacterial tracheitis. High doses of corticosteroids combined with aerosolized racemic epinephrine can relieve the respiratory difficulties.^[23]

◆ **Anne G.M. Schilder *et al.*, (2016)** reviewed Otitis Media (OM), a common middle ear inflammation seen in children. It includes acute OM (AOM), OM with effusion (OME), and chronic suppurative OM (CSOM). While OM often resolves naturally, it can lead to hearing loss, especially in developing countries. OM is usually caused by viral or bacterial infections, often following a cold. Diagnosis relies on symptoms like ear pain and hearing loss, using tools such as otoscopy and audiometry. AOM is managed with symptom relief and antibiotics in severe cases. OME is usually observed, with ventilation tubes advised for chronic cases with hearing or developmental issues. Though OM rates have declined due to better diagnosis, antibiotic use, and vaccination, it remains a major cause of medical visits and surgeries in high-income countries.^[25]

◆ **Luciara Giacobe Steinmetz *et al.*, (2009)** conducted a descriptive prospective study, on the characteristics of tinnitus in workers exposed to noise, A study conducted in 2005–2006 among 52 workers (average age 29) at a meat processing plant assessed hearing and noise exposure. While 71% had normal hearing, tinnitus was reported in 16% of males and 9% of females. The average noise exposure duration was 7 years, with levels ranging from 86 to 91 dBA in nearly half the participants. The most common tinnitus was bilateral, moderate in intensity, and described as a hissing sound. Symptoms typically began within 1 to 5 years of exposure and occurred weekly, often worsening at night. A significant correlation was found between the frequency of tinnitus episodes and noise levels. Tinnitus should be integrated into occupational hearing

loss prevention strategies to ensure more comprehensive hearing health protection for workers.^[28]

◆ **Hasan A Kalki *et al.*, (2016)** proposed a review article on Allergic Rhinitis, Allergic rhinitis is the most common atopic condition and can greatly affect a person's quality of life and productivity. Key symptoms include a blocked nose, runny nose, sneezing, and itching in the nasal area, though other symptoms may also be present. Diagnosis involves taking a detailed medical history and performing a physical exam, while also being alert for unusual or serious signs. Allergy tests, such as skin or blood tests, help confirm the diagnosis and inform treatment. Management usually involves a combination of approaches, customized to the severity of the patient's symptoms and their impact on daily life.^[29]

◆ **J.R. Kuiper *et al.*, (2018)** conducted research on Prevalence, severity, and risk factors for acute exacerbations of nasal and sinus symptoms by chronic rhinosinusitis status. In this large population-based study of 4,736 people with follow-up data, nasal and sinus symptom (NSS) severity during flare-ups was highest in those with ongoing CRS (based on EPOS criteria). Acute exacerbations (AENSS) were common across all groups, especially among current CRS cases. Seasonal patterns and risk factors for AENSS varied depending on the definition used. This first long-term study using three AENSS definitions found that NSS and AENSS are common and sometimes severe, especially with CRS. Different AENSS definitions showed varied risk associations, highlighting the need for a standardized definition.^[30]

ENT practice encompasses the management of neoplastic diseases, particularly malignancies of the oral cavity, larynx, and nasopharynx, which remain major health concerns globally. Diagnostic evaluation frequently involves endoscopic examination, audiological assessments, and advanced imaging techniques, enabling precise identification of pathologies. Therapeutic strategies range from pharmacological interventions to minimally invasive and major surgical procedures, supported by rehabilitative approaches such as speech and hearing therapy. Preventive measures, including early screening, auditory protection, and allergy management, are equally integral to ENT care. Thus, the field of Otorhinolaryngology holds a pivotal role in modern healthcare by addressing both acute and chronic conditions that significantly influence communication, respiration, and overall patient well-being.

3.2 PRIMARY CONTRIBUTORS [ETIOLOGICAL FACTORS] TO ENT-RELATED ILLNESS

3.2.1 EAR DISEASES

Otitis media is a multifactorial disease. The causes for otitis media include.

- ◆ Decreased immunity due to human immunodeficiency virus (HIV),
- ◆ Diabetes, and other immuno-deficiencies,

- ◆ Genetic predisposition,
- ◆ Mucins that include abnormalities of this gene expression, especially upregulation of MUC5B,
- ◆ Anatomic abnormalities of the palate and tensor Veli palatini, ciliary dysfunction, cochlear implants, vitamin A deficiency.
- ◆ Bacterial pathogens, *Streptococcus pneumoniae*, *Haemophilus influenzae*, and *Moraxella* (Branhamella) *catarrhalis* responsible for more than 95%, viral pathogens such as respiratory syncytial virus, influenza virus, parainfluenza virus, rhinovirus, and adenovirus, allergies, lack of breastfeeding, passive smoke exposure, daycare attendance, lower socioeconomic status, family history of recurrent AOM in parents or siblings.^[19]
- ◆ More than 90% of cases of otitis externa are due to bacteria, most commonly pseudomonas aeruginosa (22-62%) and staphylococcus aureus (11-34%). Polymicrobial infection is common.
- ◆ Fungi are rare cause of acute otitis externa (10%) and are more common cause of chronic species (10-40%).^[20]
- ◆ Otomycosis is an infection caused by a fungus. There are several different types of fungus that can cause this infection, but most otomycosis infections are related to Aspergillus species or, less commonly, Candida Species.

3.2.2 NOSE DISEASES

- ◆ Most cases of acute rhinosinusitis are caused by viral infections associated with the common cold. The most common bacterial organisms in community-acquired acute bacterial rhinosinusitis are streptococcus pneumoniae, Haemophilus influenzae, Staphylococcus aureus, and Moraxella catarrhalis.^[21]
- ◆ Rhinitis is commonly caused by a viral or bacterial infection, including the common cold, which is caused by Rhinoviruses, Coronaviruses, and influenza viruses, others caused by adenoviruses, human parainfluenza viruses, human respiratory syncytial virus, enteroviruses other than rhinoviruses, metapneumoviruses, and measles virus, or bacterial sinusitis, which is commonly caused by streptococcus pneumoniae, Haemophilus influenzae and Moraxella catarrhalis.^[22]

3.2.3 THROAT DISEASES

- ◆ The most common bacterium causing tonsillitis is streptococcus pyogenes (group A streptococcus), the bacterium that causes strep throat.
- ◆ The most common cause of a sore throat (pharyngitis) is a viral infection, such as cold or the flu.
- ◆ Most acute cases of laryngitis are caused by viral infections, the most common of which tend to be

rhinovirus, influenza virus, parainfluenza virus, adenovirus, coronavirus, and RSV.

- ◆ Common bacterial strains are group A streptococcus, Streptococcus pneumoniae, C. diphtheriae, M. catarrhalis, Haemophilus influenzae, Bordetella pertussis, Bacillus anthracis, and M. tuberculosis. In developing countries, more unusual bacterial causes may occur, such as mycobacterial and syphilitic, though these may occur in developed nations as well.^[23]

3.3 COMMON ALIMENTS MANAGED IN ENT PRACTICE

The practice of otorhinolaryngology involves diagnosis, medical treatment and surgical intervention for a variety of problems, conditions or diseases affecting ear, nose and throat as well as related areas of the neck, head and face. The word —otorhinolaryngology is made up of several Latin root words: ology means the study of the ear (oto), the nose (rhino), and the throat (larynx, as in the word larynx). this long word is frequently shortened to Otolaryngology.^[24]

3.3.1 OTITIS MEDIA

Otitis media (OM) is a group of inflammatory and complex infective conditions that affects the middle ear (comprising the middle ear cavity and ossicles). Is an umbrella term that encapsulates acute OM (AOM), OM with effusion (OME; ‘glue ear’) and chronic suppurative OM (CSOM). Acute otitis media, an infection of rapid onset that usually presents with ear pain. Otitis media typically not associated with symptoms, is defined as the presence of non-infectious fluid in the middle ear for more than three months.^[25]

Chronic suppurative otitis media (CSOM) is middle ear inflammation that results in discharge from the ear for more than three months. It may be a complication of acute otitis media. Otitis media with effusion is a condition there is a fluid in the middle ear but no signs of acute infection. As fluid builds up in the middle ear and eustachian tube, it places pressure on the tympanic membrane, this prevents it from vibrating properly, decreased sound conduction results in decreased hearing.^[26]

SIGN AND SYMPTOMS

- ◆ Ear pain, tinnitus
- ◆ Felling of fullness or pressure in the ear,
- ◆ Reduced hearing
- ◆ Fluid drainage
- ◆ Fever
- ◆ Difficulty sleeping
- ◆ Loss of balance

Figure-05: Otitis Media.

3.3.2 OTITIS EXTERNA

Otitis externa is a condition that causes inflammation (redness and swelling) of the external ear canal, which is the tube between the outer ear and eardrum. Otitis externa, commonly called swimmer’s ear, is an inflammation of the external auditory canal most commonly caused by an acute bacterial infection.^[27]

SIGN AND SYMPTOMS

- ◆ Itching in the ear canal.
- ◆ Slight redness inside the ear.
- ◆ Mild pain that is made worse by pulling on the outer ear.
- ◆ Clear fluid draining from the ear.

Figure-06: Otitis Externa.

3.3.3 TINNITUS

Tinnitus is a subjective disorder occurring in the ears in the absence of environmental noise in the form of ringing, roaring, buzzing, humming or hissing.^[28]

- ◆ Hissing
- ◆ Humming
- ◆ Whistling
- ◆ Throbbing

SIGN AND SYMPTOMS

- ◆ Buzzing
- ◆ Roaring
- ◆ Clicking

Characteristics of the sound: Can be soft or loud, Low or high-pitched, may come and go, can be heard in one or both ears, or seem to be inside the head.

Figure-07: Tinnitus.

3.3.4 ALLERGIC RHINITIS

Allergic rhinitis (AR) is an atopic disease, inflammatory disorder induced by immunoglobulin E (Ig-E) – mediated response after allergen exposure, also called as hay fever.^[29]

SIGN AND SYMPTOMS

- ◆ Nasal stuffiness (congestion), sneezing
- ◆ Runny nose,
- ◆ Itching of nose throat and eyes,
- ◆ Red or watery eyes,
- ◆ More mucus in nose and throat,
- ◆ Wheezing, coughing and trouble breathing.

Figure-08: Allergic Rhinitis.

3.3.5 RHINOSINUSITIS (SINUSITIS)

Sinusitis is the inflammation of the sinuses; the air spaces seated in the skull and facial bones. The inflammation of the sinusitis is usually accompanied by nasal inflammation due to the nature of the continuous lining mucosa, thence the most accurate name is rhinosinusitis.^[30]

SIGN AND SYMPTOMS

- ◆ Nasal congestion.
- ◆ Runny nose (rhinorrhoea)
- ◆ Postnasal drip
- ◆ Facial pain/pressure
- ◆ Facial swelling/tenderness
- ◆ Reduced sense of smell (hyposmia) or loss of smell (anosmia)
- ◆ Bad breath (halitosis)

Figure-09: Rhinosinusitis.

3.3.6 ACUTE RHINITIS

Rhinitis is classified as allergic or non-allergic. The cause of non-allergic rhinitis is usually a viral infection, although irritates can cause it. The nose is the most commonly infected part of the upper airways. Rhinitis

may be acute (short-lived) or chronic (long-standing). Acute rhinitis commonly results from viral infections but may also be a result of allergies, bacteria, or other causes.^[31]

3.3.7 PHARYNGITIS (SORE THROAT)

Pharyngitis or sore throat, is discomfort, pain, or scratchiness in the throat. It often makes it painful to swallow. Pharyngitis is characterized by swelling in the back of the throat(pharynx) between the tonsils and the voice box (larynx). Most sore throats are caused by colds, the flu, Cocksackie virus.^[32]

SIGN AND SYMPTOMS

- ◆ Sore throat, hoarse or muffled voice.
- ◆ Pain or a scratchy feeling in the throat.
- ◆ Pain that feels worse when swallowing or talking.
- ◆ Trouble swallowing.
- ◆ Sore, swollen glands in the neck or jaw.
- ◆ Swollen, red tonsils, along with white patches.

Figure-10: Pharyngitis.

3.3.8 LARYNGITIS

Laryngitis refers to the inflammation of the larynx (voice box) and can be present in both acute and chronic forms. Acute laryngitis is a mild and self-limiting condition that typically lasts for a period of 3 to 7 days. If this condition lasts for over 3 weeks, then it is termed as chronic laryngitis. The acute form of laryngitis is most common among them. The etiology for acute laryngitis can be

classified as infectious and non-infectious.^[33]

SIGN AND SYMPTOMS

- ◆ Hoarseness
- ◆ Sore or irritated throat
- ◆ Dry throat, Dry cough
- ◆ Frequent throat clearing.

Figure-11: Laryngitis.

Figure-12: Tonsillitis.

3.3.9 TONSILLITIS

Tonsillitis is inflammation of the tonsils, a common clinical condition caused by either bacteria or viral infection, tonsils are present in the upper part of the throat.^[34]

SIGN AND SYMPTOMS

- ◆ Sore throat,
- ◆ Red and swollen tonsils, and
- ◆ Difficulty swallowing. White or yellow patches on the tonsils may also be visible in bacterial infections.

3.3.10 DYSPHAGIA

Dysphagia is defined as an abnormal delay in the movement of food bolus from the oropharynx to the

stomach. Patients often report difficulty swallowing. Swallowing encompasses three phases: oral (preparatory) phase, oropharyngeal (transfer) phase, and the esophageal phase.^[35]

SIGN AND SYMPTOMS

- ◆ Pain while swallowing.
- ◆ Not being able to swallow.
- ◆ Feeling as if food is stuck in the throat or chest or behind the breastbone.
- ◆ Drooling.
- ◆ Hoarseness.
- ◆ Food coming back up, called regurgitation.
- ◆ Frequent heartburn.

Figure-13: Dysphagia.

4. METHODOLOGY

4.1 STUDY FLOWCHART

4.2 STUDY SITE

The present study was conducted in MIMS Teaching hospital. It is a 500 bedded tertiary care teaching hospital having different specialities like medicine, surgery, orthopaedics, paediatrics, obstetrics and gynaecology. This hospital provides specialized health care services to people in and around Mandya city and nearby villages.

4.3 STUDY DESIGN

This was a cross-sectional study conducted in Otorhinolaryngology department, MIMS Mandya.

4.4 STUDY PERIOD

The study was conducted for a period of 6 Months

4.5 RESEARCH PERIOD

6 Months after getting approval (4 months of data collection and 2 months for analysis and write up).

- Study population:** Patients who are visiting Otorhinolaryngology (ENT) outpatient department, MIMS, Mandya.
- Sample size:** Prescription of about 200 patients in a 4-month period.
- Sampling method:** Convenience sampling

4.6 STUDY APPROVAL

Ethical clearance was obtained from the —Ethics committee of MIMS hospital, Mandya.

4.7 STUDY CRITERIA

- Inclusion criteria**
 - Patients attending Otorhinolaryngology outpatient department with complete prescription data and given informed consent.

b) Exclusion Criteria

- Patients with incomplete data.
- Inpatients and follow up visit patients.
- Surgical patients.

c) Source of data and material

Data will be collected from patients who will be visiting ENT outpatient department, which includes social demographic details like Name, Age, Sex. It also contains details lab investigation, diagnosis, treatment and management of disease.

4.8 ANALYSIS

Descriptive Statistics like Mean has been applied in the present study. Simple percentage calculation will be conducted to arrive at the conclusion of our study. Data has been entered in Microsoft Excel and Word has been used to generate graphs, tables etc.

5. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This study was conducted in OPD of ENT department of MIMS Teaching hospital Mandya. A total of 200 patient prescription was enrolled in the study based on the criteria. The required details from patient's prescription were recorded in a suitably designed patient profile form.

5.1 DISTRIBUTION OF PATIENT BASED ON GENDER

Out of 200 prescriptions analyzed, 56% were **Male** (112 patients) and 44% were **Female** (88 patients). This indicates that males were more frequently affected by otorhinolaryngological conditions in the study population. The higher male prevalence could be due to greater exposure to occupational or environmental risk factors, lifestyle habits, or health-seeking behavior patterns.

Table 6: Distribution of patients based on gender.

GENDER	NUMBER OF PATIENTS	PERCENTAGE
Male	112	56%
Female	88	44%
Total	200	100%

Figure 14: Distribution of patients based on gender.

5.2 DISTRIBUTION BASED ON AGE GROUP

The **middle-aged group (41–60 years)** accounted for the highest proportion of patients (**32%**), suggesting increased ENT issues in this demographic, possibly linked to cumulative environmental exposures and age-

related physiological changes. The **children group (0–12 years)** was the least represented (**6.5%**), potentially reflecting lower incidence or fewer OPD visits for ENT concerns in this age range.

Table 7: Distribution based on age group.

AGE GROUP (YEARS)	NO OF PATIENTS	PERCENTAGE (%)
CHILDREN (0 – 12)	13	6.5
ADOLESCENTS (13 – 17)	15	7.5
YOUNG ADULT (18 –25)	24	12
ADULT (26 – 40)	50	25
MIDDLE AGE (41 – 60)	64	32
OLD AGE (ABOVE 60)	34	17
TOTAL	200	100

Figure 15: Distribution based on age group.

5.3 DISTRIBUTION BASED ON SYMPTOMS

The most common symptom was **bilateral earache (20%)**, followed by **throat pain (14.5%)**. Less common symptoms included **facial pain** and **swelling of the oral**

cavity (each 0.5%). This pattern suggests that ear-related complaints were predominant, possibly due to infections, allergies, or chronic ENT disorders in the community.

Table 8: Distribution based on symptoms.

SYMPTOMS	NUMBER PATIENTS	PERCENTAGE (%)
EAR ACHE	40	20
THROAT PAIN	29	14.5
DECREASED HEARING	19	9.5
THROAT IRRITATION	19	9.5
NASAL OBSTRUCTION	18	9
EAR DISCHARGE	11	5.5
NASAL DISCHARGE	11	5.5
EAR RINGING	10	5
EAR ITCHING	9	4.5
EAR TINNITUS	7	3.5
DURAL FULLNESS	5	2.5
GIDDINESS	4	2
COLD	4	2
EXCESSIVE SNEEZING	3	1.5
MOUTH ULCER	3	1.5
PAIN OVER NOSE	2	1
BURNING SENSATION OF ORAL CAVITY	2	1
CHANGE IN VOICE	2	1
FACIAL PAIN	1	0.5
SWELLING OF ORAL CAVITY	1	0.5
TOTAL	200	100

Figure 16: Distribution based on symptoms.

5.4 DISTRIBUTION BASED ON NUMBER OF PRESCRIPTION

Prescriptions most commonly contained **two drugs (28.5%)**, followed closely by **four drugs (26%)** and **three drugs (25.5%)**. The lowest frequency was **seven**

drugs per prescription (0.5%). This trend reflects a moderate polypharmacy approach, with most cases managed using a combination of two to four medications.

Table 9: Distribution based on number of drugs per prescription.

NO. OF DRUGS PER PRESCRIPTION	NO. OF PATIENTS	PERCENTAGE (%)
ONE	9	4.5
TWO	57	28.5
THREE	51	25.5
FOUR	52	26
FIVE	24	12
SIX	6	3
SEVEN	1	0.5
TOTAL	200	100

Figure 17: Distribution based on number of drugs per prescription.

5.5 DISTRIBUTION BASED ON CLASS OF DRUGS

Among **634 drugs prescribed**, **antihistamines** were most common (**25.53%**), followed by **antibiotics (19.72%)** and **analgesics (14.67%)**. The least prescribed

were **antihelminthics (0.79%)**. This highlights the frequent management of allergic and infectious etiologies in ENT practice.

Table 10: Distribution based on class of drugs.

CLASS OF DRUGS	NUMBER OF DRUGS	PERCENTAGE (%)
ANTIHISTAMINE	162	25.53
ANTIBIOTICS	125	19.72
CORTICOSTEROIDS	7	1.10
NSAIDS	58	9.15
ANALGESIC	93	14.67
PPI	79	12.47
ANTACID	26	4.10
VITAMINS	36	5.68
OTIC AGENTS	18	2.84
ANTHELMINTICS	5	0.79
OTHERS	25	3.94
TOTAL	634	100

Figure 18: Distribution based on class of drug.

5.6 DISTRIBUTION BASED ON TYPES OF ANTIHISTAMINE DRUGS

CTZ was the dominant antihistamine (80.24%), with much lower use of Montec LC (10.49%) and Ebast

(4.9%). Hicet had the lowest usage (1.85%). This preference suggests CTZ’s established efficacy, availability, and cost-effectiveness in routine ENT prescriptions.

Table 11: Distribution based on type of antihistamine drugs.

TYPES	NUMBER OF DRUGS	PERCENTAGE (%)
CTZ	130	80.24
MONTEC LC	17	10.49
EBASTINE	8	4.9
HICET (CTZ)	3	1.85
VERTIN	4	2.45
TOTAL	162	100

Figure 19: Distribution based on type of antihistamine drugs.

5.7 DISTRIBUTION BASED ON TYPES OF ANTIBIOTICS

T. Cefexime was the most prescribed antibiotic (36%), followed by T. Amoxiclav (27.2%). Least prescribed

were T. Metrogyl and T. Levofloxacin (each 0.8%). The predominance of cefexime may reflect its broad-spectrum activity and favorable resistance profile in ENT infections.

Table 12: Distribution based on type of antibiotics.

TYPES	NUMBER OF DRUGS	PERCENTAGE
T. CIPROFLOXACIN	12	9.6
T. AMOXICILLIN + CLAVULANATE	34	27.2
T. CEFEXIME	45	36
T. METRONIDAZOLE	1	0.8
T. LEVOFLOXACIN	1	0.8
T. AZITHROMYCIN	2	1.6
OIN. MUPIROCIN	3	2.4
OTODAC	7	5.6
OCUPOL	4	3.2
CIPROFLOXACIN DROPS	6	4.8
OTIFLOX	6	4.8
MOXIKIND DROPS	4	3.2
TOTAL	125	100

Figure 20: Distribution based on type of antibiotics.

5.8 DISTRIBUTION BASED ON DIFFERENT NSAIDS

T. ACSP was overwhelmingly preferred (94.82%) compared to Amber CT Gel (5.18%). This shows a strong reliance on oral NSAID formulations for pain and

inflammation control.

Table 13: Distribution based on different NSAIDS.

TYPES	NUMBER OF DRUGS	PERCENTAGE
T. ACSP	55	94.82
AMBER CT GEL	3	5.18
TOTAL	58	100

Figure 21: Distribution based on different NSAIDS.

5.9 DISTRIBUTION OF OTHER TYPE OF DRUGS CLASS

Within the "other" category, **Nasal decongestants** were most used (**40%**), followed by **H2RA (32%)**

and **proteolytic enzymes (24%)**. **Dopamine agonists** were rarely prescribed (**4%**). The prominence of nasal decongestants aligns with frequent nasal and sinus complaints in ENT settings.

Table 14: Distribution of other type of drug class.

TYPES OF DRUGS	NUMBER OF DRUGS	PERCENTAGE (%)
H2RA	8	32
DOPAMINE AGONIST	1	4
PROTEOLYTIC ENZYME	6	24
NASAL DECONGESTANT	10	40
TOTAL	25	100

Figure 22: Distribution of other type of drug class.

5.10 DISTRIBUTION OF NON-PHARMACOLOGICAL TREATMENT

Supportive therapies were also prescribed, most commonly **keeping the ear dry (42.46%)**, followed by

steam inhalation (24.66%) and **salt-water gargle (21.92%)**. This reflects a holistic management approach, integrating lifestyle measures with pharmacotherapy.

Table 15: Distribution of non-pharmacological treatment.

TYPES	NUMBER OF PATIENT	PERCENTAGE (%)
KEEP EAR DRY	31	42.46
STEAM INHALATION	18	24.66
SALT WATER GARGLE	16	21.92
SOFT DIET	8	10.96

Figure 23: Distribution of non-pharmacological treatment.

5.11 DISTRIBUTION BASED ON GENERIC AND BRAND NAME

Majority of drugs were prescribed by **GENERIC NAME (96.05%)**. **BRAND NAME** prescribing was very low

(3.95%). High **GENERIC** prescribing is in line with WHO recommendations and reduces treatment cost. Small use of **BRAND NAMES** may be due to availability issues or prescriber preference.

Table 16: Distribution based on generic and brand name.

GENERIC /BRAND	NUMBER OF DRUGS	PERCENTAGE (%)
GENERIC	605	96.05
BRAND	29	3.95
TOTAL	634	100

Figure 24: Distribution based on generic and brand name.

5.12 DISTRIBUTION BASED ON DIFFERENT DOSAGE FORM

Tablets dominated prescriptions (72.88%), followed by capsules (12.46%) and drops (9.46%). The least used

was spray (0.15%), typically for nasal issues. This suggests a strong preference for oral solid dosage forms due to patient convenience and compliance.

Table 17: Distribution based on different dosage form.

DOSAGE FORM	NUMBER OF DRUGS	PERCENTAGE (%)
TABLET	462	72.88
CAPSULE	79	12.46
DROPS	60	9.46
SYRUP	26	4.10
OINTMENT	3	0.47
GEL	3	0.47
SPRAY	1	0.15
TOTAL	634	100

Figure 25: Distribution based on different dosage form.

5.13 WHO CORE PRESCRIBING INDICATOR

Average NUMBER OF DRUGS PER PRESCRIPTION: 3.17 (higher than WHO standard 1.6–1.8). ANTIBIOTIC USE: 19.72% (within WHO range 20–26.8%). INJECTION USE: 0% (lower than WHO range

13.4–24.1%, expected in OPD ENT cases). This is because the data was collected from OPD Department. GENERIC PRESCRIBING: 95.43% (close to WHO ideal 100%). ESSENTIAL MEDICINE LIST prescribing: 94.95% (close to WHO ideal 100%).

Table 18: Distribution based on WHO core prescribing indicators.

INDICATORS	STANDARD VALUE	OBSERVED VALUE
Average number of drugs per prescription	1.6- 1.8	3.17
Percentage of encounter of antibiotic	20 - 26.8%	19.72%
Percentage of encounter of injections	13.4 – 24.1	0%
Percentage of Drug prescribed Generic Name	100%	95.43%
Percentage of drugs Prescribed from essential medicine list (EML)	100%	94.95%

6. CONCLUSION

Our study was mainly focused on the prescribing pattern of drugs in the outpatient ENT department and the distribution of otorhinolaryngological conditions. This study reveals that most of the drugs were prescribed in oral solid dosage forms, and the majority of prescriptions followed the WHO Essential Drug List (India, 2019), which is a positive finding that supports rational drug use. The number of drugs prescribed by their generic names was much higher compared to brand names, thereby reducing the economic burden on patients and most of these medicines were made available free of cost through the hospital pharmacy.

Ear-related complaints, particularly earache, were reported most commonly among the study population, while throat and nasal conditions were also frequently observed. This may be attributed to environmental exposure, lifestyle factors, or recurrent infections. Hence, clinical pharmacists and healthcare providers should play an important role in patient education, emphasizing preventive measures such as maintaining ear hygiene, avoiding allergen exposure, and adhering to supportive therapies like steam inhalation and salt-water gargling.

Overall, evaluation of prescribing patterns not only helps in monitoring rational drug use but also improves the quality of prescriptions, reduces unnecessary polypharmacy, and promotes cost-effective therapy. Performing this kind of drug utilization studies periodically ensure adherence to WHO prescribing indicators and optimize patient care in the ENT outpatient setting.

7. SUMMARY

The present study was conducted in the ENT outpatient department of MIMS Teaching Hospital, Mandya. During the study a total of 200 patient prescriptions were analysed, out of that 56% were male and 44% were female, indicating that males were more frequently affected by otorhinolaryngological conditions. With respect to age distribution, the middle-aged group (41–60 years) constituted the highest proportion (32%), whereas children (0–12 years) found to be the least (6.5%). Upon Symptom analysis it revealed that bilateral earache (20%) was the most common presenting complaint, followed by throat pain (14.5%), while facial pain and swelling of the oral cavity (0.5% each) were the least common.

Prescribing pattern analysis showed that the majority of prescriptions contained two drugs (28.5%), with most prescriptions ranging between two to four drugs, reflecting moderate polypharmacy. Out of 634 drugs prescribed, antihistamines were the most frequently used class (25.53%), followed by antibiotics (19.72%), analgesics (14.67%), and proton pump inhibitors (12.47%). The least prescribed were anthelmintics (0.79%). Among antihistamines, cetirizine dominated (80.24%), while among antibiotics, cefixime (36%) and

amoxiclav (27.2%) were most preferred. NSAID use was almost exclusively restricted to T. ACSP (94.82%). Other less commonly used drugs included nasal decongestants (40% of —other category), H2 receptor antagonists (32%), and proteolytic enzymes (24%).

Regarding dosage forms, tablets were the most commonly prescribed (72.88%), followed by capsules (12.46%) and drops (9.46%), with sprays being rarely used (0.15%). Prescribing habits also showed rationality, as 96.05% of drugs were prescribed by generic name. In addition to pharmacological therapy, non-pharmacological measures were also prescribed in 73 cases, with keeping the ear dry (42.46%) being the most common supportive advice, followed by steam inhalation (24.66%) and salt-water gargling (21.92%).

Evaluation of WHO core prescribing indicators demonstrated that the average number of drugs per prescription was 3.17%, which was higher than the WHO standard of 1.6–1.8. The percentage of antibiotic encounters were 19.72%, which lies within the WHO recommended range (20–26.8%). Injection use was 0%, which is lower than the WHO range (13.4–24.1%) but expected in an OPD setting. Generic prescribing was 95.43% and prescribing from the essential medicine list was 94.95%, both of which are close to WHO recommendations.

Overall, the study highlights that ear-related complaints were the most common in the ENT OPD, antihistamines and antibiotics were the dominant therapeutic classes, and prescribing practices largely adhered to rational drug use principles, with high generic prescribing, minimal brand use, and integration of supportive non-pharmacological therapy.

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